

Impact of Air Inlet Shape and Position on the Total Drag of Hydrogen Fuel Cell Propulsion Aircraft Nacelle

Adarsh Prasannakumar^{*†} and Peter Scholz^{*}

**Institut für Strömungsmechanik, TU Braunschweig
Hermann-Blenk-Straße 37, 38108 Braunschweig*

a.prasannakumar@tu-braunschweig.de · p.scholz@tu-braunschweig.de

[†]Corresponding author

Abstract

This paper presents the aerodynamic design and analysis of the oxygen air inlet for a fuel cell-based regional aircraft. RANS simulations are conducted using the SU2 solver, with the propeller modelled as an actuator disk. The computational approach is validated against experimental data for both the actuator disk and representative inlet geometries. Two inlet shapes, namely a stagnation type S-bend and a submerged trapezoidal design, are evaluated for pressure recovery, drag, and flow distortion. The study identifies trade-offs associated with inlet placement downstream of the propeller, serving as a foundation for future inlet shape optimisation.

1. Introduction

To achieve the emissions target set by Flightpath 2050, which includes 90% NOX reduction and 75% CO2 reduction compared to baseline aircraft of 2000, a significant stride towards electrification of commercial aviation is required [1]. The use of hydrogen fuel cells for the propulsion system, as proposed in the Clean Aviation project titled Fuel Cell Propulsion System for Aircraft Megawatt Engines (FAME), shows significant promise [2]. Preliminary studies with fuel cell propulsion suggest that the technology has the potential to achieve the emission targets for the regional flight [3].

However, the integration of hydrogen fuel cell systems into aircraft presents unique design challenges, particularly concerning the subsystems of the fuel cell system. One subsystem that presents a significant design hurdle is the air inlet system that supplies oxygen to the fuel cell stack and the aerodynamic penalties associated with it. The fuel cell system requires a continuous supply of oxygen for the electrochemical reaction, demanding a dedicated air intake and compressor system to meet the specific pressure and mass flow requirements of the fuel cell system [4]. This dedicated air supply system adds wetted area and complexity to the aircraft structure. Furthermore, the placement of the intake, particularly behind the propeller in its high-energy slipstream, introduces complexities related to flow distortion, pressure recovery for the subsequent compressor, and ultimately, aerodynamic drag [5]. Therefore, the design and integration of the air intake becomes a critical factor in ensuring the overall aerodynamic performance and operational efficiency of hydrogen fuel cell aircraft.

This study focuses on the aerodynamic integration of the subsystem of the hydrogen fuel cell propulsion systems, specifically investigating the impact of the air inlet design and its position relative to the propeller on the total drag. Through a comprehensive computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis, the study explores various inlet configurations, aiming to identify designs that minimise drag penalties while ensuring adequate mass flow rate and flow quality for the fuel cell system.

2. Methodology

2.1 Baseline geometry

Figure 1 shows the nacelle of the fuel cell aircraft considered in the current study. The nacelle is the research baseline adapted by DLR-AS based on aircraft pre-design conducted by the University of Naples Federico II (UNINA) within the FAME project. Two intakes are provided on the port and starboard sides of the nacelle to supply cold air to the heat exchanger of the fuel cell. To reduce the computational effort, the heat exchanger is not completely modelled in the

IMPACT OF AIR INLET SHAPE AND POSITION ON DRAG

study. However, the intake and outlet part of the heat exchanger duct is taken into account. The air flow inside the heat exchanger duct is simulated with the help of inlet and outlet boundary conditions specified on the faces depicted in red colour. The reference parameters at cruise conditions used for the current study are tabulated in Table 1.

Figure 1: Baseline geometry of the nacelle with heat exchanger duct

Table 1: Parameters for baseline nacelle at cruise condition

Parameter	Value	Units
Propeller thrust	8095	N
Propeller diameter	3.97	m
Angular speed	850	RPM
Reference area	55	m ²
Freestream temperature	234.658	K
Reynolds length	3.97	m
Reynolds number	22.54 Million	
Mach number	0.55	-

2.2 Computational method

The impact of the air inlet shape and position is determined using a Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) based CFD analysis with the help of the open-source solver SU2. The propeller is modelled as an actuator disk based on the general momentum theory [6]. The actuator disk model already implemented in the solver will be used for this purpose. The analysis is performed for cruise conditions of the aircraft. Therefore, steady-state conditions can be assumed, and the angle between the disk and the freestream is considered to be negligible.

The study is organised into two parts. The first part deals with validating the computational method and analysing the clean nacelle configuration. Validation is carried out for the actuator disk model using previous experimental data available for the SAAB SF-340 nacelle [7]. To validate the modelling of the air inlet, the reference S-bend and trapezoidal inlet geometries are compared to the experimental data from the literature.

In the second part, the scaled S-bend inlet is integrated into the nacelle at different positions. The distance of the air inlet from the propeller is varied, and aerodynamic performance is compared for the same target mass flow rate through the air inlet.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Validation studies

This section presents the validation of the CFD solver SU2, used in the current study. Two validation case studies are conducted to ensure the validity of the actuator disk model and the reliability of the CFD model in predicting the pressure recovery of the air inlet.

3.1.1 Actuator disk model

The actuator disk model used in the study is validated against experiments performed by Samuelson on the scale model of the SAAB SF340 propeller as shown in Fig. 3 [7].

Figure 2: Dimensions of wind tunnel model of SAAB SF340 (adapted from [7])

The propeller is modelled as an actuator disk using the thrust coefficient, power coefficient and advance ratio, assuming a minimum interference propeller. Table 2 shows the parameters used for validating the actuator disk model.

Table 2: Modelling parameters for the actuator disk model based on SAAB SF-340

Parameter	Value
Thrust coefficient	0.234
Power coefficient	0.227
Advance ratio	0.705
Reynolds number	1.66 Million
Mach	0.15

The simulations were conducted at three different angles of attack, ranging from 0 degrees to 10 degrees. Figure 3 shows the variation of the pressure coefficient on the actuator disk surface. As the angle of attack increases, the down-moving blades experience an increased effective angle of attack, leading to a higher lift force. This results in an increase in side force in the Y-direction.

The force coefficients measured in the wind tunnel experiment along the three axes are compared with the values estimated in the current study. The comparison is shown in Fig. 4. The simulation model demonstrates good agreement with the experimental data.

3.1.2 Design of air inlet

Air inlet design significantly impacts three key parameters that influence the energy efficiency of the aircraft. These performance parameters are total pressure recovery, aerodynamic drag, and flow distortion. High total pressure re-

IMPACT OF AIR INLET SHAPE AND POSITION ON DRAG

Figure 3: Pressure coefficient contour on the actuator disk for different angle of attack

Figure 4: Variation of force coefficient in the Y direction with angle of attack (AoA)

(a) Force coefficient in the X direction

(b) Force coefficient in the Z direction

Figure 5: Variation of force coefficient in X and Z direction with angle of attack (AoA)

covery is particularly desirable, as it reduces the power required by the compressor. To maximise pressure recovery, stagnation-type or scoop-type inlets are typically employed, offering values approaching unity. However, this performance benefit often comes at the expense of increased aerodynamic drag. Conversely, submerged inlets, such as the NACA and trapezoidal configurations, tend to produce lower drag but achieve reduced pressure recovery. Accurate CFD modelling of both inlet types is essential to reliably predict the pressure recovery and drag characteristics, thereby

enabling effective integration into propulsion systems.

Therefore, a validation of the simulation for the two inlet types has been carried out. As a first case, the S-bend geometry similar to the previous work of Aslan et al., is selected [8]. Figure 6 shows the computational domain of the S-bend inlet geometry.

Figure 6: CAD geometry and computational domain of the S-bend inlet

Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) simulations are performed for a Mach number of 0.207. The total conditions are specified at the far-field boundary, with a freestream pressure of 1×10^6 Pa. No-slip boundary conditions are applied on the inlet wall, and a symmetry plane is defined to reduce computational cost. The Jameson Schmidt Turkel (JST) central scheme is employed for the discretisation of convective fluxes, with default values used for the scalar dissipation coefficients. Turbulence is modelled using the Spalart-Allmaras (SA) turbulence model and discretised using a scalar upwind scheme.

Figure 7 shows the Mach contour on the symmetry plane and the streamlines inside the inlet. The velocity increases as it enters the inlet due to the reduction in area and decreases towards the exit. The diffusing section of the S-bend inlet leads to a small separated flow towards the end of the inlet. Table 3 shows the comparison of pressure recovery at the outlet boundary face of the current simulation compared to that of the experimental data. A good agreement between the simulation and experiment is obtained.

Figure 7: Mach contour and streamline for the S-bend validation simulation

Similar analysis is now performed on a submerged type air inlet. A trapezoidal shape of the submerged inlet

IMPACT OF AIR INLET SHAPE AND POSITION ON DRAG

Table 3: Total pressure recovery at outlet face

Parameter	Experiment (reference)	Simulation
Pressure recovery	0.9798	0.983

provides a short leading edge in comparison to the trailing edge, leading to deviation of the boundary layer away from the intake. This reduces the effect of the intake on the freestream [9]. Furthermore, the sharp side edges generate counter-rotating vortices leading to entrainment, thereby allowing improved mass flow to the inlet [10]. In the current study, the optimised trapezoidal submerged inlet shape from the previous work conducted by Ahmed is taken as the reference [9]. Figure 8 shows the trapezoidal intake geometry used in the current study.

Figure 8: CAD geometry and computational domain of the trapezoidal intake

Three geometric parameters influence the performance of the trapezoidal intake. The side edge angle (ξ) shows the deviation of the side edge of the trapezoid from normal to the leading edge. The side edge angle affects vortex strength, thereby influencing both mass flow rate and flow mixing. The optimal side edge angle varies in the range of 3-6 degrees. The ramp angle of the intake affects the pressure gradient normal to the freestream direction. The shape of the aft lip impacts the flow behaviour, especially the distortion coefficient at the exit plane of the intake. The geometric parameter selected for the current study is also depicted in Fig. 8. The shape of the aft lip is determined as a lemniscate curve function with control parameter $\theta = 30^\circ$ and offset $\delta = 0.3$ mm.

RANS simulations are carried out at a Mach number of 0.7 and a Reynolds number of 15.6 million. The angle of attack of 4 degrees is used for the validation to the experiment measurement carried out by Sun et al. [11]. No-slip condition is specified on the walls and the half model is simulated using the symmetry boundary condition. Static pressure at the outlet face is defined as 80% of the freestream total pressure. A comparative study between first-order and second-order upwind schemes has been conducted. It was observed that the first-order Advection Upstream Splitting Method (AUSM) upwind scheme was not able to accurately capture the counter-rotating vortex originating at the entry of the inlet. Therefore, the MUSCL reconstruction option provided in SU2 was then used to get second-order accuracy for the AUSM scheme.

Figure 9 shows the comparison of Mach streamlines for different numerical schemes and turbulence models. In contrast to the AUSM scheme, the AUSMPLUSUP scheme (AUSM+up, revised Mach and pressure splitting) offers better convergence and low fluctuations in velocity, particularly near the low velocity zone close to the outlet plane. Finally, a comparison between Spalart-Almaras and SST $k - \omega$ turbulence model is also conducted.

Figure 10 shows the comparison of momentum vectors for SA and SST turbulence models for the trapezoidal inlet. SA model predicts a higher momentum into the inlet due to a stronger vortex compared to the SST model. This leads to a relatively larger separated area prediction for the SA model.

IMPACT OF AIR INLET SHAPE AND POSITION ON DRAG

Figure 9: Comparison of Mach streamlines for the trapezoidal inlet using different numerical schemes and turbulence models

Figure 10: Flow comparison within the trapezoidal intake using Spalart-Allmaras (SA) and SST turbulence models, illustrated by momentum vectors

The Mach contours shown in Fig. 11 indicate that the Spalart-Allmaras (SA) model predicts higher flow velocity near the lip region, attributable to an increased mass flow rate compared to the SST model. However, the velocity distribution at the outlet plane is similar for both models, with small regions of elevated Mach number observed near the lower portion in the SA case. The pressure recovery values obtained from both turbulence models are compared with the experimental data of Sun et al. in Table 4. Pressure recovery demonstrates good agreement with the reference measurements for both models, with deviations of approximately 0.5%. This suggests that the choice of turbulence model has a limited impact on the estimation of pressure recovery.

IMPACT OF AIR INLET SHAPE AND POSITION ON DRAG

Figure 11: Mach contour comparison for SA and SST scheme on the symmetry and outlet planes

Table 4: Total pressure recovery at outlet face

Parameter	Experiment (reference)	Simulation (SA)	Simulation (SST)
Pressure recovery	0.915	0.912	0.910

3.2 Analysis of baseline geometry

The next part of the study focuses on the analysis of the baseline nacelle geometry with the simplified heat exchanger ducts (Fig.1). Simulations have been performed for cruise conditions at Mach 0.55 using the SA (SA-neg) turbulence model. The total pressure inlet condition is specified for the two HEX outlet faces. A static pressure is defined as the outlet boundary condition for the HEX inlet. These pressure boundary conditions are iteratively adjusted to obtain a target mass flow rate.

The placement of the inlet in different positions of the baseline nacelle will influence the overall lift and drag of the configuration. Therefore, a sensitivity study is performed to determine the change in lift and drag for off-design conditions during cruise by considering an angle of attack deviation of ± 0.5 degrees. It was observed that the drag coefficient exhibits a maximum variation of approximately 7 drag counts with slight positive angles of attack of 0.5 degrees. The increase in drag is mainly due to the flow separation occurring near the upper trailing edge of the nacelle and the altered flow behaviour in the region between the outlet ducts of the heat exchanger (HEX) along the central line. The lift and drag coefficients computed at zero degrees angle of attack for the baseline nacelle configuration will serve as the reference values for subsequent air inlet studies. Table 5 summarises the aerodynamic parameters estimated for the sensitivity study.

Table 5: Aerodynamic performance parameters of the baseline nacelle configuration

Parameter	AoA = -0.5 degree	AoA = 0 degree	AoA = 0.5 degree
Lift coefficient, C_l	-0.00129	-0.00041	0.00036
Drag coefficient, C_d	0.0045	0.0047	0.0054

3.3 Inlet position study

The stagnation type S-bend inlet geometry is selected as the primary design for the air inlet for the fuel cell due to its higher pressure recovery values. The reference presented in Section 3.1.2 is scaled to accommodate the increased mass flow requirement of 1.2 kg/s for the fuel cell. Figure 12 shows the scaled air inlet designed for the current study. The area at the exit plane of the air inlet is 0.03 m².

Figure 12: Adapted S-bend inlet geometry

In the present study, the position of the air inlet is varied along the symmetry plane of the nacelle downstream of the propeller. To enable a meaningful comparison between these positions, the entry face of the air inlet is consistently aligned tangentially to the local curvature of the nacelle at each location. The effectiveness of the air inlet is quantified using three performance metrics: pressure recovery, drag contribution, and flow uniformity. The swirl flow induced by the propeller, as well as the local static pressure field near the inlet, can significantly influence its effectiveness. The first part of the study compares the effectiveness of the air inlet when positioned at the same axial distance from the propeller on the upper and lower surfaces of the nacelle. Figure 13 shows the static pressure coefficient on the upper and lower sides of the nacelle along the vertical symmetry plane. It can be observed that the static pressure initially decreases as the flow accelerates over the propeller hub. The propeller, modelled as an actuator disk, introduces a sudden rise in static pressure corresponding to the imposed thrust and power coefficients.

Figure 13: Pressure coefficient on the surface of the nacelle along vertical symmetry plane ($Y=0$)

IMPACT OF AIR INLET SHAPE AND POSITION ON DRAG

Figure 14 compares the Mach number contours for Case P1, with the air inlet positioned on the upper and lower surfaces of the nacelle. It can be observed that the inlet placement introduces additional blockage, resulting in higher local velocity near the sides of the air inlet. The Mach contours, plotted at the inlet entry plane, indicate that the flow does not exhibit symmetrical behaviour and is offset relative to the symmetry plane. The inlet located on the upper surface of the nacelle displays a low-velocity region to the left of the inlet entry. This trend is mirrored for the configuration with the inlet on the lower surface. This asymmetry arises due to the swirl component of velocity introduced into the flow by the propeller.

Figure 15: Mach contour on the exit boundary of the air inlet

The Mach vector at the exit boundary of the air inlet is shown in Fig. 15. The arrows indicate the direction of the flow vorticity. The geometry of the S-bend, combined with the flow offset caused by the swirl induced by the propeller, results in a non-uniform velocity profile at the outlet. This non-uniformity is quantified using the distortion coefficient

parameter, DC60. DC60 is defined as the ratio of the difference between the average total pressure and the lowest average total pressure in 60-degree sector to the dynamic pressure on the exit plane. Equation 1 is used to calculate the value of DC60.

$$DC60 = \frac{p_{0,out} - \min(p_{60^\circ,out})}{q_{out}} \quad (1)$$

The inlet positioned on the lower surface of the nacelle at P1 results in a 40% higher DC60 value compared to that of the inlet on the upper side. The total drag coefficients of the upper and lower variations for case P1 are comparable. However, the pressure recovery for the lower surface inlet exhibits an increase of approximately 0.6% relative to the upper surface configuration. The selection of inlet placement may therefore be guided by the weighted point rating method proposed by Kazula et al. [5]. In this method, greater weight is assigned to total pressure recovery (28%) and drag (17%), while distortion contributes only 6% to the overall score. Consequently, the inlet placed on the lower surface at section P1 offers a marginal overall advantage. Additionally, the lower placement facilitates easier integration of an inertial particle separator, which can provide cleaner air to the fuel cell.

In the second part of the study, the axial distance of the air inlet downstream of the propeller is varied. The position of the inlet is modified along the lower surface of the nacelle in increments of 0.5 m, up to a maximum distance of 2.4 m. Four positions (P1, P2, P3, and P4), as shown in Fig. 13, are selected such that the static pressure coefficient varies from positive to negative values. Figure 16 shows the comparison of the skin friction coefficient of the four different inlet position variations on the lower surface of the nacelle. It can be observed that shifting the air inlet further downstream leads to an increase in the velocity. This increase in velocity delays or prevents flow separation near the heat exchanger outlet ducts, thereby reducing pressure drag while increasing the skin-friction drag of the nacelle.

Figure 16: Skin friction coefficient contour for inlet position variations on the lower surface of the nacelle

The contribution of the air inlet to the overall drag is estimated to be an order of magnitude lower than that of the nacelle. Shifting the air inlet towards a region of locally low static pressure increases its pressure drag contribution. The contributions from the skin friction on the inlet surface and the momentum at the exit boundary remain effectively constant, as the targeted mass flow rates are similar across all four cases. Pressure recovery exhibits a decreasing trend with increasing distance from the propeller. This variation is consistent with expectations, as greater energy is required to extract air from a region of lower static pressure. Figure 17 shows the comparison of pressure recovery and overall drag of the nacelle inlet combination.

IMPACT OF AIR INLET SHAPE AND POSITION ON DRAG

Figure 17: Pressure recovery and drag coefficient for inlet position variation on the lower surface of the nacelle

Figure 18: Mach contour on the out boundary for air inlet positions on the lower surface of the nacelle

The four air inlet configurations examined in this study exhibit a similar flow pattern at the exit boundary, characterised by a small vortex region near the upper side, as shown in Fig. 18. As previously discussed, the S-bend geometry of the air inlet induces rotational flow, resulting in a distorted velocity profile. However, the estimated distortion coefficient for all four cases remains approximately constant, within the range of 0.3. This indicates that the distortion coefficient is primarily governed by the inlet geometry rather than its axial position. These findings suggest that further optimisation of the inlet shape, tailored to the local flow field, could enhance the overall aerodynamic performance.

4. Conclusion

The paper presents an aerodynamic analysis of various air inlet configurations designed to supply oxygen to a fuel cell system integrated into a regional aircraft nacelle. The CFD model, incorporating the actuator disk model, was validated using the SU2 solver against experimental data of the scaled model of the SAAB SF-340 propeller. The actuator disk formulation demonstrated good agreement with experimental force coefficients across a range of angles of attack, thereby confirming the reliability of the simplified propulsion model.

Subsequent validation was performed on two types of air inlets: a stagnation-type S-bend inlet and a submerged trapezoidal intake. Simulations for both geometries were compared against prior experimental and numerical studies, confirming the ability of the solver to predict pressure recovery accurately. While the S-bend inlet demonstrated higher pressure recovery, it also exhibited higher flow distortion due to its internal curvature. In contrast, the trapezoidal inlet exhibited lower pressure recovery, but a favourable drag performance could be expected along with enhanced mass flow via vortex-induced entrainment effects. The selection of the turbulence model and numerical schemes had a significant impact on local flow features, including the strength and separation prediction. However, these models exerted only a minor influence on the global pressure recovery values. The simulation methodology was then employed to establish a benchmark simulation for the baseline nacelle configuration, incorporating the sensitivity to angle of attack at cruise conditions. The estimated lift and drag coefficients were utilised as the reference for the air inlet analysis.

A parametric study was conducted in order to investigate the effects of inlet position on pressure recovery, aerodynamic drag, and flow distortion. The axial shift of the air inlet downstream of the propeller increased local flow acceleration and induced separation near the inlet edges. However, axial positions closer to the pressure minimum led to a reduction in separation near the heat exchanger outlet region of the nacelle, which translated into modest gains in lift. The drag penalty associated with moving the inlet downstream was relatively small in the range of 2 drag counts between the extreme positions. This suggests that further shape optimisation at each location could yield beneficial trade-offs. Further analysis revealed that the distortion coefficient remained largely insensitive to the inlet's axial position, instead being predominantly influenced by the S-bend geometry. This suggests that significant gains in effectiveness may be achieved through careful optimisation of the inlet shape, tailored to the local aerodynamic environment.

Overall, the study highlights the importance of integrated air inlet design for hydrogen fuel cell propulsion systems. Future work will focus on detailed shape optimisation of the inlet under varying flight conditions.

5. Acknowledgments

The authors would also like to acknowledge Mario Di Stasio (UNINA) for the pre-design of the aircraft and Florian Schmidt (DLR-AS) for kindly providing the baseline nacelle geometry. We would also like to acknowledge the funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Climate, Energy and Mobility grant agreement No: 101140559 (FAME). Finally, the authors acknowledge the provision of computing time on the high-performance computer "Lise" at NHR Center ZIB.

References

- [1] Clean Sky 2 First Global Assessment 2020: Technology Evaluator Report. <https://www.clean-aviation.eu/news-events/technology-evaluator-first-global-assessment-2020-technical-report>. Accessed: 21-05-2025.
- [2] Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking. <https://clean-aviation.eu/>. Accessed: 27-11-2024.
- [3] Martin Hepperle. Electric Flight - Potential and Limitations. 10 2012.
- [4] Stefan Kazula. Common Cause Analysis of the Air Supply System of Fuel Cell-Powered Propulsion Systems in Electrified Aviation. *Engineering Failure Analysis*, 163, 05 2024.
- [5] Stefan Kazula and David Hintermayr. Conceptual Design and Evaluation of Air Inlets of Fuel Cell-Powered Electric Aero Engines for Regional Aircraft. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2716, 03 2024.
- [6] Ettore Saetta, Lorenzo Russo, and Renato Tognaccini. Implementation and Validation of a New Actuator Disk Model in SU2. In *SU2 Conference 2020*, 06 2020.
- [7] Ingemar Samuelson. Low Speed Wind Tunnel Investigation of Propeller Slipstream Aerodynamic Effects on Different Nacelle Wing Combinations. *International Council of Aeronautical Sciences, ICAS*, 1988.

IMPACT OF AIR INLET SHAPE AND POSITION ON DRAG

- [8] Samet Aslan, Dilek Kurtulus, Ender Hepkaya, and Sefa Yilmazturk. Numerical Investigation of a Serpentine Inlet Validated with Experimental Results for Different Turbulence Models. *Advances in Sustainable Aviation*, pages 129–137, 01 2018.
- [9] Ali Ahmed. *Adjoint Based Aerodynamic Shape Optimization of Subsonic Submerged Intake*. PhD thesis, Middle East Technical University, 06 2021.
- [10] Alvin H. Sacks and John R. Spreiter. Theoretical Investigation of Submerged Inlets at Low Speeds. In *Technical Note NACA-TN-2323*, 08 1951.
- [11] Shu Sun, Rong-Wei Guo, and Yi-Zhao Wu. Characterization and Performance Enhancement of Submerged Inlet with Flush-Mounted Planar Side Entrance. *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, 23(5):987–995, 2007.